

Deliverable

Project Acronym:	ImAc
Grant Agreement number:	761974
Project Title:	<i>Immersive Accessibility</i>

D1.1-Consortium operating procedures.

Revision: 1

Authors: Jose Miguel Sanjuan (I2CAT)

Delivery date: M1 (31-10-2017)

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 761974		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	x
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Abstract: This deliverable is a handbook addressed to the consortium members to have a common understanding of the project procedures, complementing the information of the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. The handbooks summarize the main points to consider regarding the project structure, collaborative tools for communication, project reporting, dissemination contractual rules and internal procedures.

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	5-9-17	Jose Miguel Sanjuan	I2CAT	First draft
0.2	30-10-17	Jose Miguel Sanjuan	I2CAT	Second draft
0.n				
...				
0.9				
1.0				
1.x				

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable, is written by the **ImAc** (*Immersive Accessibility*) – project consortium under EC grant agreement H2020 – ICT2016-2 761974 and does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Statement of originality:

This document contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ImAc is a project that comes together different actors from the European research ecosystem: universities, private companies, non-profit organizations, and research centres. This deliverable aims to provide a comprehensive document that addresses the internal operation procedures, the roles and responsibilities of each partner, internal protocols for reporting and the contractual obligations as collected in the CA and GA.

The main topics included in D1.1 are:

- Description of the responsibilities of the different roles and bodies as defined in the Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement.
- Project reporting procedures and the editorial criteria for addressing the project outputs.
- Communication procedures, including meeting protocols and voting rules.
- Contractual obligations in the dissemination actions.

CONTRIBUTORS

First Name	Last Name	Company	e-Mail
Jose Miguel	Sanjuan	I2CAT	jose.miguel.sanjuan@i2cat.net

CONTENTS

Revision History	1
Executive Summary.....	2
Contributors	3
Tables of Figures and tables	6
List of acronyms.....	7
1. Project structure and documents of reference.	8
1.1. Project structure.....	8
1.2. Bodies and roles.	9
1.3. Documents of reference.	11
1.3.1. Grant Agreement.....	11
1.3.2. Consortium Agreement.....	12
1.3.3. Additional documentation.	12
2. Reporting.....	13
2.1. General rules.	13
2.2. Events that must be immediately reported.....	13
2.3. Project Reporting Calendar.....	13
2.4. Project monitoring (QMR).....	15
2.5. Deliverables.....	16
2.5.1. Deliverable Acceptance Process	16
2.5.2. Editorial standard and Quality criteria.....	17
2.6. Milestones.....	17
2.7. Periodic reporting.....	17
2.7.1. The Periodic Technical report.....	18
2.7.2. Individual Financial Report:.....	18
3. Collaborative platform, communication and Meetings.	20
3.1. Collaborative platform.....	20
3.2. Communication.	20
3.2.1. E-mail Communication	20
3.3. Calendar.....	21
3.4. Meetings.	21
3.4.1. Hosting a face to face meeting.....	21
3.4.2. Voting rules.....	22
4. Dissemination	23

4.1.	Acknowledgements.	23
4.1.1.	Publications, conferences and events.....	23
4.1.2.	Patents and standards:	23
4.1.3.	Communications, major results, equipment.....	24
4.2.	Output reporting.	24

TABLES OF FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1-Project Management Structure.	8
Figure 2- Structure Confluence.....	20
Table 1-Project scheduling	15
Table 2-Deadline internal reporting	15
Table 3- Deliverable review work-flow.	17

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
GA	General Assembly
PC	The Project Coordinator
MST	Management Support Team
TM	Technical Manager
TCC	Technical Coordinator Committee
IEIPM	Exploitation and IP Manager
EA	Ethical Advisor
ECGA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
DOA	Description of the Action
LEAR	Legal authorized representative
QPR	Quarterly Periodic Report.

1. PROJECT STRUCTURE AND DOCUMENTS OF REFERENCE.

In this section the project structure and the responsibilities of the bodies and roles defined in the project are described. In first place we summarize the decision-making structure and the responsibilities of the bodies and of the appointed roles. In second place we describe the documents that define the rights and obligations of each partner and project body.

1.1. Project structure.

The *General Assembly (GA)* is the ultimate decision-making body and will be responsible for monitoring, controlling the project development and will manage any conflict that may arise. The *Project Coordinator (PC)*, assisted by the *Management Support Team (MST)*, will coordinate the reporting and be the contact point with the EC. The *Technical Manager (TM)* will coordinate the technical work and will chair the *Technical Coordinator Committee (TCC)*, composed by one representative from each beneficiary along with the EA, the IEIPM and the PC. This body is responsible of implementing the decisions of the GA and of monitoring the technical activity. The *Exploitation and IP Manager (IEIPM)*, will do a permanent screening of the sector, and is in charge of the exploitation, dissemination of the foreground generated in the project, assessing the consortium about IP issues. The *Ethical Advisor (EA)* will supervise and advice about the ethical procedures.

The current members of the different boards can be found in the confluence space of the project.

Figure 1-Project Management Structure.

1.2. Bodies and roles.

General Assembly (GA)	Project coordination committee.
Chaired by	The Project Coordinator (PC).
Participants	GA comprises one senior representative of each Partner.
Meeting frequency	At least twice a year.
Responsibilities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Content, finances and intellectual property rights: Approve changes to annexes 1 and 2 of the ECGA, changes to the Consortium plan, and any modifications to the attachments 1, 2 and 3 of the CA. 2. Evolution of the Consortium: Entry of a new party to the Consortium, withdrawal of a party, identification of a breach by a party, any action related with a defaulting party (declaration, remedies, and termination), change of coordinator, request of suspension or termination of the project. 3. Appointment of the Technical committee members (if necessary). 4. Evaluate proposal made by the TCC

Technical Coordinator Committee (TCC)	Supervisory body for the execution of the project.
Chaired by	Technical Coordinator
Participants	PC, TC, IEIPM, EA, one representative per partner.
Meeting frequency	At least monthly
Responsibilities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implement the decisions of the GA. 2. Monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the project. 3. Collect monthly information on the progress of the Project, evaluate the information and propose any modification to the GA. 4. Support the coordination in preparing meetings with the EC and in preparing related data and deliverables. 5. Prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications. 6. Rearrange funding and effort of abolished tasks.

Project Coordinator (PC)	Co-ordinates the communication channels within all the partners to ensure progress and quality in the work and provides the Commission with technical, managerial and financial information.
Contact	sergi.fernandez@i2cat.net
Responsibilities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitor that the actions is implemented properly. 2. Act as the intermediary for all communications between the beneficiaries and the Commission. 3. Collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Funding Authority. Submit the deliverables and reports to the Commission. 4. Ensure that all payments are made to the other beneficiaries without unjustified delay and inform the Commission of the amounts paid to each beneficiary. 5. Monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations. 6. Keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available 7. Transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned 8. Administering the financial contribution of the Funding Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks described in the CA 9. Providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.

Management Support Team	Gives support to the Project Coordinator in all his responsibilities.
Contact	jose.miguel.sanjuan@i2cat.net
Responsibilities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assist the Project Coordinator in the project management tasks. 2. Manages the delivery and the follow-up of administrative and financial documents. 3. Is a permanent contact point for the Coordinator and all the Partners regarding their participation in the project, responding to any relevant requests and maintaining a high level of communication within the Consortium. 4. Is in charge of the day-to-day project management, prepares the needed logistical, legal and administrative documents and will supervise the overall running of the project. It also provides support and assistance to the different project bodies 5. Is responsible for ensuring that all of the administrative steps required for effective progress of the project will be fulfilled in good time. The MST gets advice from financial, legal, IPR specialists whenever required.

Technical Manager (TM)	The TM will coordinate the technical activities providing quality assurance and ensuring scientific rigour and formal evaluation.
Contact	thopesch@irt.de
Responsibilities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Chair of the TCC. 2. Liaisons between the TCC and the GA. 3. Supervision of the overall technical progress of the project. 4. Consolidation of the technical reports. 5. Follow-up and coordination of all technical work-packages(WP 2 5)

Exploitation and IP Manager (IEIPM)	The IEIPM will ensure that the knowledge gained in ImAc will be exploited and disseminated for the maximum benefit of the participants and society.
Contact	enric@anglatecnic.com
Responsibilities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensuring that the knowledge will be exploited and disseminated for the maximum benefit of the participants and society. 2. Assessing all Parties for protecting the Intellectual Property derived 3. Permanently screening the market with a view to find new opportunities to increase the Project impact.

Ethical Advisor (EA)	The EA is responsible for the proper management of all ethics procedures.
Contact	pilar.orero@uab.cat
Responsibilities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensuring the proper management of all ethics procedures 2. Supervising all actions related with users 3. Providing advice and recommendations on ethics to all Parties and the Coordinator

1.3. Documents of reference.

The two documents that define the rights and obligations of IMAC partners are the Grant Agreement (ECGA) which defines the legal compromises of the consortium with the EC and the Consortium Agreement (CA), an internal agreement between the consortium members.

1.3.1. Grant Agreement.

The Grant Agreement (ECGA) sets out the rights and obligations and the terms and conditions applicable to the grant awarded to the beneficiaries for implementing the action. Is signed by the EC and the beneficiaries of the action. It has seven parts

- Terms and Conditions
- Annex 1 Description of the action (DOA)
- Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action & Additional information on the estimated budget
- Annex 3 Accession Forms
- Annex 4 Model for the financial statements
- Annex 5 Model for the certificate on the financial statements (CFS)
- Annex 6 Model for the certificate on the methodology

During the project the consortium members need to be especially familiar with the Terms and Conditions and the DoA.

The **Terms and Conditions** fixes, among other items, the budget, the duration of the action, the conditions for the costs to be eligible, the rights and obligations of the parties, payment arrangements and the rights and obligations related with background and results, recruitment, and gender equality.

The **Description of the Action (DoA)** is divided in two parts. Part A provides details on the deliverables, milestones, participation of each partner in every WP, effort by partner and WP, task description, implementation risks and a tentative schedule of the project reviews. Part B includes the objectives of the action, the expected impact and how to measure it, the implementation strategy, the resources to be committed and a description of the members of the consortium.

Any modification of the Grant Agreement must be approved by the General Assembly, the EC and implemented through an amendment of the document. The latest version of the document will be uploaded in the Participant Portal and in confluence.

1.3.2. Consortium Agreement.

The purpose of the Consortium Agreement (CA) is to specify with respect to ImAc the relationship among the Parties, in particular concerning the organisation of the work, the management of the Project and the rights and obligations of the Parties concerning inter alia liability, access rights and dispute resolution. The CA is based in an adaptation of the DESCA 1.2 model.

Any modification of the Grant Agreement must be approved by the General Assembly and implemented through an amendment of the document. The latest version of the document can be found in the intranet of the project (confluence).

1.3.3. Additional documentation.

In order to facilitate the management of the project additional information covering financial management, administrative management, dissemination guidelines etc. will be regularly uploaded in the management section of the confluence.

2. REPORTING

2.1. General rules.

Reporting is a process that concerns the full consortium, and every partner is responsible for the quality of their contribution. English is the official language in IMAC, and all relevant documents and written communications will be written in English. Dissemination materials can be translated to other languages, being each partner responsible of the translation to its language of interest.

2.2. Events that must be immediately reported

As stated in the GA, the Partners must inform immediately the PC, who will inform the PO and the Consortium of any events which are likely to affect significantly or delay the implementation of the action or the EU's financial interests:

- Change of the PI or LEAR.
- Changes in its legal, financial, technical, organizational or ownership situation or those of its linked third parties and
- Changes in the name, address, legal form, organization type of its linked third parties;
- Any circumstance affecting the de decision to award the grant or compliance with the requirements under the agreement.

In addition, each beneficiary must keep information stored in the Participant Portal up to date.

2.3. Project Reporting Calendar.

The list of official commitments is summarized in Table 1.

Month	Month (ii)	Events
1	oct.-17	D1.1 Consortium operating procedures (I2cat)
	oct.-17	1.Kick-off meeting (i2cat)
3	dic.-17	D1.2 Ethical considerations and Data Management Plan (i2cat)
	dic.-17	D6.2 Operational public website with logo (uab)
	dic.-17	4.user centred methodology defined (rbb)
	dic.-17	D6.1 Dissemination plan (RNIB) (1st interact)
	dic.-17	D2.1. Used centered design (UAB) (1st interact)
4	ene.-18	1st QPR
	ene.-18	D2.2. User requirements (RBB) (1st interact)
5	feb.-18	D2.3. Platform Specification (CCMMA) (1st interact)
6	mar.-18	5.first specifications and architecture ready (RBB)
	mar.-18	15. workshop 1
	mar.-18	D3.1. Architecture design (USAL) (1st inter)
7	abr.-18	6. Evaluation and execution plan ready (CCMA)
	abr.-18	2nd QPR
	abr.-18	D5.1 Pilot operation plan (CCMMA) (1st interact)

	abr.-18	D5.2 Pilot evaluation methodology and plan (UAB) (1st interact)
9	jun.-18	D3.5 Player (i2cat) 1st interaction
	jun.-18	D3.2 Content Manager (ANGLA) (1st inter)
	jun.-18	D3.3 Content packaging and distribution (MSE)(1st inter)
10	jul.-18	7. First integration successfully achieved (i2cat)
	jul.-18	8. Edition tools and 1st content ready for pilot 1 (IRT)
	jul.-18	3rd QPR
	jul.-18	D3.6 Integration and testing report (USUAL) (1st inter)
	jul.-18	D4.1 Subtitle Production tools (IRT) (1st inter)
	jul.-18	D4.2 Audio Production Tools (IRT) (1st inter)
	jul.-18	D4.3 Sign Language Editor (Angla)
	jul.-18	D4.5 Accessibility Service Tools reports (ANGLA) (1st inter)
11	ago.-18	D5.3 Pilot Content (RBB) (1st interact)
12	sep.-18	D 1.4.Management and Periodic Report - First Period (i2cat)
	sep.-18	9. Pilots 1st interaction finished and evaluated (CCMA)
	sep.-18	End period 1
	sep.-18	16. workshop 2
13	oct.-18	D2.1. Used centered design (UAB)
	oct.-18	4th QPR
	oct.-18	D5.4 Pilot Evaluation Report (UAB) (1st interact)
14	nov.-18	D2.2. User requirements (RBB)
	nov.-18	Subm.1st periodic report+ Financial report
15	dic.-18	D2.3. Platform Specification (CCMMA)
	dic.-18	D1.4 Management and periodic report- First period
	dic.-18	2.mid term review successfully achieved (i2cat)
16	ene.-19	D3.1. Architecture design (USAL)
	ene.-19	D6.4 Short movie
	ene.-19	10. second specifications and architecture ready (RBB)
	ene.-19	5th QPR
	ene.-19	D6.3 Updated 'plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results' (1st interact)
18	mar.-19	D6.1 Dissemination plan (RNIB)
19	abr.-19	D3.2 Content Manager (ANGLA)
	abr.-19	D3.3 Content packaging and distribution (MSE)
	abr.-19	D3.4 Accessibility interface (IRT)
	abr.-19	D3.5 Player (i2cat) 2nd interaction
	abr.-19	6th QPR
20	may.-19	D3.6 Integration and testing report (USUAL)
	may.-19	D4.4 Report on new accessibility formats (IRT)
	may.-19	12. second integration successfully achieved (i2cat)
	may.-19	17. workshop 3
21	jun.-19	D5.1 Pilot operation plan (CCMMA)
	jun.-19	D5.2 Pilot evaluation methodology and plan (UAB)
	jun.-19	11. Evaluation and execution plan updated for iteration 2 (ccmma)
22	jul.-19	7th QPR
24	sep.-19	D 1.3.Progress Activity Report (i2cat)

	sep.-19	D4.1 Subtitle Production tools (IRT)
	sep.-19	D4.2 Audio Production Tools (IRT)
	sep.-19	D4.3 Sign Language Editor (Angla)
	sep.-19	D4.5 Accessibility Service Tools reports (ANGLA)
25	oct.-19	D5.3 Pilot Content (RBB)
	oct.-19	13. Edition tools and 1st content ready for pilot 2 (IRT)
	oct.-19	8th QPR
28	ene.-20	9th QPR
30	mar.-20	D 1.5 Final management and Periodic Report (i2cat)
	mar.-20	D5.4 Pilot Evaluation Report (UAB)
	mar.-20	D6.3 Updated plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results'
	mar.-20	3.organization of final review (i2cat)
	mar.-20	14. pilots 2nd iteration finished and evaluated
	mar.-20	Final QPR

Table 1-Project scheduling

2.4. Project monitoring (QMR).

In order to effectively monitor the evolution of the project, the partners will be asked to fill-in through confluence a Quarterly Progress Report (QPR). The schedule of reporting will be as follows:

Month	Events	Covering	deadline
ene.-18	1st QPR (D1.3)	Months 1-3	15/01/2018
abr.-18	2nd QPR (D1.3)	Months 3-6	15/04/2018
jul.-18	3rd QPR (D1.3)	Months 7-9	15/07/2018
oct.-18	4th QPR (D1.3)	Months 10-12	15/10/2018
ene.-19	5th QPR (D1.3)	Months 13-15	15/01/2019
abr.-19	6th QPR (D1.3)	Months 16-18	15/04/2019
jul.-19	7th QPR (D1.3)	Months 19-21	15/07/2019
oct.-19	8th QPR (D1.3)	Months 22-24	15/10/2019
ene.-20	9th QPR (D1.3)	Months 25-27	15/01/2020
mar.-20	Final QPR (D1.3)	Months 27-30	15/03/2020

Table 2-Deadline internal reporting

The QPR includes the following parts. Information will be reported through confluence.

- Summary of the project progress: Responsibility of the PC.
- Work achieved by Work Package: Short report describing the work progress during the period. Responsibility of each WP leader.
- Summary of the dissemination activities. Responsibility of each partner.
- Estimation of the effort expended by WP and beneficiary. Responsibility of each partner.
- Summary of the status of deliverables and milestones. Responsibility of the MST.

2.5. Deliverables.

This section describes the deliverables that ought to be submitted during the project in due time (end of the month indicated in the DoA).

The deliverables are either labelled as *Report*, as *Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP)*, *Other* or as *Websites, patents filling*. In all the cases a report using the appropriate template must be followed. The definitive version of the deliverables will be uploaded to confluence by the PC.

The Dissemination level can be *Public* or *Confidential* (EC and members of the Consortium). In the case of confidential deliverables, the partners will avoid sharing information through Google Drive. For public deliverables, once have been submitted to the EC the definitive content will be shared internally with the Consortium through confluence. If there are not written objections, public deliverables will be uploaded to the project webpage. Public deliverables will be published by the EC once have been approved.

2.5.1. Deliverable Acceptance Process

A clear process has been defined for the final acceptance of a deliverable. The responsibilities in the consortium are the following ones:

- The **Editor** (appointed by the **lead partner** of the deliverable) has to propose a TOC as soon as possible. It is recommended to be at least 180 days before the deadline. He will propose to the rest of the consortium a distribution of the tasks and it will verify the contents of the documents assuring that the information contained is accurate and in line with the editorial standards (see next section).
- The **Reviewer** will be appointed by the PC being a team member from a partner involved in the deliverable's edition but not contributing to it. The reviewer will make revision of the deliverable and assess if some modifications are needed. The reviewer will assure the conformity of the document with the quality criteria (see next section)
- To comply with article 8.4.1 of the CA the editor will send to the consortium at least 20 days before the submission, the final draft of the deliverable.
- The final submission of the deliverable will be made by the **PC**.

Action	Days to deadline	Responsible	Receiver
TOC, section assignment to partners,	180 days	Lead beneficiary (editor).	Partners involved+WPL involved+TM
First consolidated draft of the deliverable + initial feedback from editor	90 days.	Lead beneficiary (editor).	Partners involved+WPL involved+TM
Second consolidated draft of the deliverable	60 days.	Lead beneficiary (editor).	Partners involved+WPL involved+TM
Final draft (ready to be send to reviewers)	30 days	Lead beneficiary (editor).	Partners involved+WPL involved+TM
Reviewers feedback	15 days.	Reviewers.	Editor.
Revised inputs	10 days.	All authors.	Editor.
Final consolidated draft	4 days.	Editor.	PC.

Table 3- Deliverable review work-flow.

2.5.2. Editorial standard and Quality criteria

The **editor and the reviewer** must take into account the following criterions against which every single deliverable will be evaluated The **editor** has to verify that the contents are detailed in the correct way:

- **Content.** The deliverable must address the objectives specified in the DOA. It should have accurate information with respect to the scope and purpose, provide information and be focused on the key aspects of the deliverable scope.
- **Accuracy.** The information provided in the deliverables should be supported by accurate information, with the appropriate references. Foreground and results, should be clearly identified and technically supported.
- **Format.** Each deliverable must be produced using the deliverable template

In addition, the **reviewer** specifically has to verify the following formal checkpoints:

- That the deliverable includes an executive summary and proper conclusions if necessary.
- The contribution of each partner involved is correctly reported.
- The impact of the deliverable and any progress beyond the state-of-the-art has to be clearly identified. Any expected output (paper, patents, standard...) has to be included.
- Clear and correct language is used, appropriate abbreviations and references are included and listed, a logical order is followed and that the document follows the style guideline.

2.6. Milestones.

Deliverables will be marked as achieved by the PC in SYGMA. At least with two days in advance of the deadline the lead beneficiary of the milestone will send the PC and the TM a short paragraph explaining the arguments that support the achievement of the milestone. In case that is necessary, the Lead Beneficiary will provide as support the necessary documents or reports that will be keep by the PC.

2.7. Periodic reporting.

The Periodic Reporting is submitted through the SYGMA by the PC. There are two Periodic Reports, first one covering the activity and costs of months 1 to 12 (submission 29-11-18), second one covering months 14 to 30 (submission 30-5-20). Along with the second Periodic Report a Final Report will be submitted.

The periodic reporting has two main parts (i) the Periodic Technical report which contains a progress report detailing the work carried out during the period reported and the financial statements that declare the expenses during the period. Submitting this reports is a contractual obligation with the EC.¹

¹ An extended explanation of each item that covers the reporting can be find [here](#). This section is a summary of the information provided by the EC.

2.7.1. The Periodic Technical report

The periodic technical report is sub-divided in 2 parts:

PART A to be filled in on-line into the SYGMA system, it is composed by the following sections:

1. **Publishable summary** –Stand-alone document that must be written in a language easily understandable by broader public.
2. **Deliverables:** Summary of the status of the deliverables
3. **Milestones:** Summary of the status of the milestones.
4. **Critical implementation risks and mitigation actions:** State of play of every risk identified in Annex 1 and if necessary new mitigation measures.
5. **Publications:** List of the scientific publications related with the project. For reporting the publications, a DOI is mandatory.
6. **Dissemination and exploitation of results:** Broader vision of the dissemination and communication activities specifying (i) total funding amount (ii) the number of Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the project by category, (iii) the estimated number of persons reached.
7. **Patents:** List of patents.
8. **Innovation:** Any prototypes, new products launched to the market, innovations introduced in private companies.
9. **Impact on SME:** Evolution of turnover and employees of the SMEs
10. **Open Data:** Open data information
11. **Gender.**

PART B: Is a textual report of the activities carried out by the consortium during the reporting period. This document includes the following parts:

1. Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and overview of the progress, including justification of the deviations
 - 1.1. Objectives. List of objectives and the work carried out to fulfil them.
 - 1.2. Explanation of the work carried per WP detailing the contribution of each beneficiary
 - 1.3. Impact.
2. Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results.
3. Update of the data management plan.
4. Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous review(s) (if applicable)
5. Deviations from Annex 1 (if applicable)
 - 5.1. Tasks: Provide details of tasks not fully implemented, deliverables not submitted or objectives not achieved.
 - 5.2. Use of resources: Explanation on how the financial resources have been used and any possible deviation.

2.7.2. Individual Financial Report:

At the end of Period 1 (M1-M12) and Period 2 (M13-M30), each partner will provide the Financial Statements to the coordinator. The FS will include the costs of the period and will be declared in order to claim reimbursement to the European Commission. The FS will be complemented with an audit certificate when accumulated funding surpasses 325.000 €.

The following rules must be specially taken into account when addressing the financial report.²
Each partner:

1. Shall be solely responsible for **justifying its own costs**, (not the EC contribution) that must be (i) Linked with the project (ii) Incurred by the beneficiary. (iii) Incurred during the duration of the Project. (iv) According to usual practices of the beneficiary. (v) Reasonable and justified. (vi) Identifiable and verifiable
2. **Can only report eligible direct costs**: Those costs that are specifically incurred because of carrying out an action (personnel, travel, equipment, consumables, minor tasks, other...). Indirect Costs (overheads) is a Flat Rate of 25%. Non-Eligible costs cannot be reported (Dividends, Interests, provisions, debts, Exchange losses, bank Commissions, excessive costs, deductible VAT...)
3. The beneficiaries must declare costs based on the **actual amounts spent**
 - a. Personnel Costs based on actual staff costs. See article 6.2.A of the ECGA for more information on how to calculate personnel costs.
 - b. Other direct costs based on actual costs for the project
 - c. Depreciation costs for assets
 - d. Real costs of consumables

More information can be found in the Confluence / WP1 Management / Documentation / Webinar on financial reporting.

² Please refer to Article 6 of the [AMGA](#) for full details.

3. COLLABORATIVE PLATFORM, COMMUNICATION AND MEETINGS.

3.1. Collaborative platform.

The infrastructure chosen to hold the documentation produced by the project will be based on the Confluence solution by Atlassian that will be used as project collaborative platform of the project. A shared Google Drive will be used for any intermediate documents.

<https://confluence.i2cat.net/display/IMA/ImAc+Home>

The Project Coordinator (PC) and the Technical and Technical Manager (TM) will be the ultimate responsible for maintaining the contents, organization and availability to the partners. Any news user must be informed to the MST who will The platform has the following sections:

- WP1. Summary of WP and milestones
 - Deliverables WP1: The definitive version of the deliverables.
 - Documentation: Up-to-date versions of the GA, CA and useful information.
 - Gantt chart
 - ImAc Templates: latest version of the templates of the deliverables, minutes, posters, presentations...
 - Meetings and minutes WP1
 - Reporting: QPR reporting will be done through here.
 - Task 1.1-Administrative, financial and contractual management
 - Task 1.2-Reporting and controlling: QPR will be reported through here
 - Task 1.3-Quality management
 - To do WP1
- WP2 to WP6
 - Deliverables: last version of the deliverables
 - Meetings and minutes
 - Task n.1-
 - Task n.2-
 - Task n.n-
 - To do WPn
 -

Figure 2- Structure Confluence

3.2. Communication.

3.2.1. E-mail Communication

The email communication reflector of the project will be hosted by the Coordinator, i2CAT who established and maintains the following email lists imac-all@i2cat.net

All emails sent to the reflector will include the following text in brackets in the subject [IMAC], [IMAC-WPX] etc.

In case a new member joins the project, an email with the specific request should be sent to the MST who will include it in the corresponding section. An updated list of all the contacts can be found in the confluence site.

3.3. Calendar.

An updated calendar will be maintained by the MST that will include reminders of the main deadlines. The calendar is linked to a google calendar where the changes must be done.

3.4. Meetings.

Meetings can be either face to face or virtual meetings. For each meeting the following documentation will be produced and uploaded on the respective folder in the document repository of confluence

- **Notifications:** All formal face to face meetings (GA, TCC, etc.) will be notified at least three weeks in advance. Virtual meetings will be notified at soon as possible.
- **Documentation:** Agenda and supporting documentation will be available to all attendees at least one week before the face to face meeting. Issuing of all documents will be via the chairman, who is responsible for compiling all submissions from partners and will be appointed at the beginning of the meeting. In virtual meeting's agenda and discussions points will be shared as soon as possible through confluence.
- **Minutes:** All meetings (face to face or not) will be formally minuted. The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall produce written minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. The draft minutes shall be available through confluence within 10 calendar days of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days, no member has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson.

The accepted minutes will be accessible from the documents repository in the confluence.

- Face to face minutes will include a list of participants on each day of the meeting. Remote minutes will have to include a list of the participants attending to the call.

3.4.1. Hosting a face to face meeting.

During the project, members may host project meetings. The hosting partner has to take into consideration the following points:

- It is advisable that the location can be reachable to avoid extra costs. It has to provide logistic information on how to reach the venue of the meeting.
- The costs of hosting the meeting will be covered by the hosting partner and the travel costs will be covered by each participant.
- The host must provide meeting rooms with audiovisual equipment necessary for the presentations and network connectivity.
- It is also recommended (general practice although not obligatory) to provide water, coffee breaks and lunch and organize one social event (e.g., invite partners for one evening meal).

3.4.2. Voting rules.

In the event that is needed to vote a decision, each body has to take into consideration the quorum and the voting rules. The quorum for both the TCC and the GA is two-thirds of its members are present or represented. In the GA each member present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote. The PC shall have double vote in case of a tie. Decisions in the GA shall be taken by a majority of three-fifths of the votes cast. Decisions in the CA shall be taken by consensus.

A member which can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of a Consortium Body may exercise a **veto** with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision. How to apply the veto and some specific cases on how to vote are specified in 6.2.3 of the CA.

4. DISSEMINATION

Dissemination of the project results, whenever is possible and suitable, is one of the objectives included in the ECGA. Dissemination however must not collide with the IPR of the partners or with results that need to be protected. See ECGA and CA for more information.

In this section we describe the mandatory rules for disseminating the results of the project. Dissemination strategy will be further complemented by deliverable D6.1 *Dissemination Plan (M3-18)* and D1.2 *Ethical considerations and Data Management Plan (M3)*.

4.1. Acknowledgements.

All the publications, conference proceedings, presentations on workshops, seminars, press releases, equipment, communications, patents, standard or public events must take into account the following obligation towards the EC (see article 29 and 38 of the ECGA).

4.1.1. Publications, conferences and events

Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

(a) display the EU emblem and

(b) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761974”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission.

This does not however give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

(...)

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.³

4.1.2. Patents and standards:

Application for protection of results (including patent applications) filled by or in behalf of a beneficiary must include the following:

“The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761974”.⁴

If results could reasonably be expected to contribute to European or international standards, the beneficiary concerned must inform the Commission (up to four years after the end of the

³ Extract from Article 29 ECGA

⁴ Extract from article 27 ECGA.

project), and ask the standardisation body to include the following statement in (information related to) the standard:

“Results incorporated in this standard received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761974”.⁵

4.1.3. Communications, major results, equipment

Any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must **inform the PC** and

(a) display the EU emblem and

(b) include the following text:

For communication activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761974”.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results:

“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761974”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission.

(...)

Any communication activity related to the action must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.⁶

4.2. Output reporting.

It is a contractual obligation for the members of the consortium to inform of any foreseen publication with at least 45 days in advance. Objections must be done within 30 days after the reception of the notice. Objections must follow the arrangements stated in article 8.4 of the CA.

In addition, in each QPR publications, conferences, book chapters, assistance to workshops, conferences, seminars and any other event linked with the dissemination have to be reported to the MST through confluence.

Press releases, press campaigns, media appearance must be communicated as soon as possible to the MST to be included in the website and disseminated through the media tools.

<end document>

⁵ Extract from article 28 ECGA.

⁶ Extract from article 38 ECGA.